

ORGANIZED CORRUPTION: ANALYSING THE NEXUS

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INTRODUCTION²

Corruption is one of the main challenges to the rule of law, life chances and people's livelihoods in the Western Balkans. It is both a cause and consequence of a criminal culture that permeates the region, and the way that corruption is linked to politics suggests a degree of organized corruption, and even elements of state capture, in a number of countries in the region. Typical manifestations of high-level organized corruption in the six countries of the Western Balkans (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia) are Wild West-style selling and buying of public property by political elites and their associates in the business and criminal spheres; corrupt tendering for infrastructure projects (such as construction of roads); inside deals struck with loyal partners, either for procurement or privatization processes; concealment of ownership; fraud and embezzlement of public funds; non-disclosure (or false disclosure) of assets; money laundering (both locally and offshore); and abuse of public office.

The systemic threat posed by corruption in the region is also evident when individuals or entities finance political parties in return for favours. These include undeclared sources of funding; the buying of political support by handing out gifts and favours; and using public funds, and appointments in the civil service or state-owned enterprises as tools to build a patronage network of political dependency. In this way, political, business and criminal elites collude to preserve and protect their interests and influence over public functions and resources. These practices create a fertile environment for corrupt officials to operate with impunity. Despite the severity of the problem, society in the region seems to have become inured to the reality of high-level state corruption. There is a pervasive sense that this is just the way things are and the system cannot be changed. This learned helplessness is perpetuated by a lack of independence or professional capacity within institutions whose role it is to tackle corruption. There are few convictions in high-profile cases of organized corruption yet draconian restrictions

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imposed by the authorities on the media, including threats and sanctions against those who speak against political abuses, politically and business linked organized crime and high-level organized corruption.

There are two dominant types of corruption:

Conventional corruption, bribery and nepotism are culturally well entrenched and often go hand in hand with malfunctioning public administration.

Organized Corruption is the involvement and/or use of an interest organization, criminal or not, in various forms of corruption and related illicit deeds from the position of power and/or with political coverage to gain financial, political or social benefits. Organized corruption rests on the interwoven criminal, political and economic interests to profit from the power position and political coverage of illicit deeds.³ Key types of organized corruption in the Western Balkans include:

ILLUSTRATIONS OF ORGANIZED CORRUPTION

Political financing – political parties and elections

Control over and abuse of public (state-owned) enterprises

Misuse and control over public procurements

As WB 6 countries seek to promote and safeguard the transparent, responsible and accountable financing of political parties and elections, as well as the management of SOEs and public procurement, it is possible to summarize the main challenges they face regarding their legislative frameworks, their compatibility with international – and in particular EU – standard guidelines and protocols, and the institutional architecture of oversight and control.

Legislation

All six countries in the Western Balkans have legislation regulating the financing of political parties and elections. However, there are consistent shortcomings in terms of implementation, even after recommendations have been made by European institutions such as the Council of Europe and the OSCE. Even WB6 countries that have laws in line with European and international standards sometimes fail to live up to them due to insufficient oversight from relevant bodies or regulatory agencies, many of which lack independence. Poor integrity and rather high levels of corruption within each Western Balkan country detract from achieving international standards in the financing of political parties and elections.

Internal oversight and accountability for finances within political parties themselves need to be strengthened. Loopholes detected within each jurisdiction seem to show a lack of understanding or willingness to provide transparency in bookkeeping in relation to the financing of political parties and elections. Each national report demonstrates how political parties made use of loopholes and how provisions were

³ In purpose for deeper scientific consideration of the practical consequences from the complexity of high-level institutional type of organized corruption see: Miodrag Labovic: Policing in Central and Eastern Europe – Social Control of Unconventional Deviance, Conference Proceedings, Social control of institutional organized crime, 2011, <https://www.ncjrs.gov/pdffiles1/nij/Mesko/235122.pdf>, pp.194 -208

misused or ignored in practice in order to achieve more support and seats in government. The lack of appropriate oversight or sanctioning, even when irregularities are discovered, does not help achieve international standards or the implementation of satisfactory provisions. Case law usually shows harsher punishments for parties that no longer hold power. Although the legislative arena regarding public enterprises looks relatively well developed, it still suffers from notable shortcomings, particularly when it comes to the implementation and application of effective and independent oversight and control bodies and the selection of the best professionals for roles within SOEs.

One common shortcoming is the political appointment of key managers and other employees within an SOE, which often seems based more on political allegiance than skill. Another is the lack of respect for the findings of control and oversight bodies and the subsequent implementation of remedies to improve the situation. Yet another notable deficiency concerns the almost complete lack of transparency in relation to operations, appointments and the reporting of results. Similarly, there is also a lack of public accountability, including, in some instances, limited access to data; in some countries, there are not even accurate accounts of the number and sectoral distribution of SOEs.

In each of the WB6 countries, public procurement is exposed to corruption. Considerable efforts have been undertaken to align legislation with EU law in an expression of political willingness and the desire to be seen as seriously devoted to the values and expectations of the EU and UN. The alignment of laws on public procurement with EU standards is still an ongoing process in the Western Balkans.

Most countries established their relevant legislative frameworks in the initial years of the 2000s, and all countries have since passed amendments aimed at improving transparency and integrity and reducing risks of corruption.

However, the legislative route has not always been unidirectional towards reducing corruption opportunities related to public procurement. For example, as noted earlier, Serbia's legal framework obliged the Public Procurement Office to appoint a representative of a civil society organization, an academic or an expert knowledgeable in public procurement as a civic observer in all public procurement procedures over €8.5 million. The civil observer reported directly to the Parliamentary Committee on Finances. However, in the last revision of the legislation, and through the adoption of the current Law on Public Procurement in 2019, this institute and obligation were removed from Serbian legislation. Moreover, in a number of laws, convenient legal windows – or loopholes – were introduced. There is a need for further in-depth 'corruption proofing' of public procurement related legislation.

Control and oversight

When it comes to political party financing, control and inspection are performed by CECs in Albania, BiH and Kosovo. In Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia, this task is performed by agencies or commissions for the prevention of corruption, as well as by state audit offices. WB6 countries have adopted new laws and a number of controls based on EU recommendations, but implementation is lagging. The constitutional set-up of BiH (three entities and cantons in the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina) poses a special complication, with inconsistent legislation and a lack of supervision and competence of behalf of the CEC. Supervision is more successful during election campaigns at all levels, but the pre-election period and control over media advertising still pose problems. Albania has implemented the latest legislation with a three-tiered approach,

which appears to be an interesting control model. ⁴Civil society's role as an oversight actor is very important throughout the Western Balkans and needs to be further enhanced and institutionalized, particularly in view of the influence of political parties over other control institutions.

Transparency is lacking, and SOEs are rarely held accountable. In North Macedonia, for example, although the Law on Public Enterprises and the Company Law oblige SOEs to submit quarterly financial reports to the government and publish them on their official websites, the enterprises rarely release these reports to the public. The Law on Free Access to Information of Public Importance in Serbia aims to strengthen transparency in this regard. Nevertheless, it has been reported that since the law's adoption, SOEs have been ignoring most information requests, even to the extent of ignoring requests submitted by the Commissioner for Information of Public Importance. Almost identical problems plague public procurement.

Implementation

Most legislation is generally in line with international standards, but there are marked problems with the implementation of laws. There are therefore a number of loopholes in the legislation that need to be addressed. Too often, political parties deliberately bypass the law to promote their own financial interests and impact election results and power-based decision-making. In such situations, the role of control and oversight mechanisms is of utmost importance, although they cannot alone impose and safeguard transparency, responsibility and accountability. Many of the control structures are themselves politicized and therefore no longer impartial; some are not independent or lack sufficient financial support and capacity to carry out their functions.

Control over political financing must necessarily deal with corruption and money laundering, yet most of the control structures and procedures related to the political financing of parties and elections are rather limited. Both political parties and the people that run them are potentially corrupt, and there is evidence that much of the money in politics flows through private pockets rather than party treasuries. Treating the financing of political parties as separate from the control of political officials' property and of public contracting, especially public procurement leaves any system of control invalid and consequently inefficient. Inefficient control mechanisms, prosecutions and courts add impunity to the failure of anti-corruption measures in the financing of political parties.

There is ample evidence of increased spending on social media advertising, particularly on Facebook, in all recent electoral campaigns, yet many relevant pieces of legislation lack references to sponsoring political campaigns on social media. There are also numerous examples of media being misused in political campaigns. Some electoral lists delayed reporting their advertisements as political, thereby avoiding making the details of such advertising public. Some election participants reported lower than actual costs for field campaigns and the production of promotional videos. Some media outlets discounts to certain political parties or provided services that were not defined in their

⁴ About deeper structural reforms in 9 crucial systems and 50 subsystems for effective fight against systemically endemic and institutional organized corruption in North Macedonia and similar countries in WB, see in: Миодраг Лабовиќ, "Системско владеење на правото против системската корупција и организирианиот криминал- Стратешка визија со конкретни реално одржливи и практично спроведливи решенија за нашите најголеми проблеми- Како Македонија може да стане функционална држава", Култура Скопје, 2024, стр. 281-562

price lists, while others broadcast political marketing without having submitted price lists by the legally defined deadline.

Electoral marketing campaigns often consist, in part, of opening or initiating public infrastructure works, such as roads, bridges, railways, high-speed trains, shopping centres or factories, which are financed from the state budget but are functionalized to achieve an electoral advantage for the parties in power. Similarly, as the state is still the biggest employer in Western Balkan countries, public administration employees are often asked to attend the governing party's political rallies; transport, food, drinks and even per diems are sometimes provided, either at the expense of the enterprises or the donors. In some countries, an increase or the promise of an increase in pensions or other social welfare entitlements has become an integral part of electoral campaigns.

Public opinion survey companies can greatly influence public preferences in electoral campaigns. Some political parties have their own survey companies, while others contract specialized opinion survey companies. The financing of such activities and the specific favourable targeting of the results need particular scrutiny. Considering the wide use and impact of social media and surveys, this is an area of urgent and increased concern.

All country reports noted the need to reform the political financial reporting system into a transparent, interactive, user-friendly and easy-to-monitor electronic system. Thus, the creation of online platforms to host all the data so that it could be found and easily monitored and analysed would be of great help. Online political finance reporting and disclosure systems are part of broader transparency efforts to make official data more available and accessible to the public, and they contribute to efforts to increase the capacity and professionalism of candidates and political parties. As such, they are important modern technological tools to strengthen the political financing information database and allow systematic and transparent control and oversight.

The influence of organized crime on politics in WB6 countries has been addressed in a previous series of GI-TOC reports, *Infrastructure of Integrity*, but it is worth underlining that the impact during elections has become more sophisticated. Often, hidden support is provided to political parties by placing organized crime associates from certain professions or families on the electorate. In some cases, members of organized crime or hooligan groups have been used to maintain order and discipline among political supporters or at protest demonstrations for political parties or movements. The financing of political parties and elections is still subject to corruption and organized crime, which is becoming more intricate and difficult to trace.

The financing of political parties in all WB6 countries is regulated by law and distinguishes between government budgetary financing at the state, regional and municipality levels. Other financing in some countries, mainly B and H, Serbia and Kosovo, also comes in the form of membership fees, donations, income from property and events, inheritances, legacies and bank loans. The maximum funding that a political entity can collect from private sources depends on various parameters. According to available data, countries are harmonizing legislation with EU standards, but implementation is problematic. In principle, budgetary funding is not a problem, except for parties that do not reach the funding threshold and have non-parliamentary party status. Financing from private funds, especially donations, is more ambiguous and problematic as it allows for more creativity and concealment of funds and cash flows. Prohibitions on funding from international individuals, foreign legal entities, political parties and NGOs are a grey area.

Sanctions are also problematic in the analysed countries, as they are mostly only monetary and have no political effect.

When it comes to the implementation of legislative provisions, several shortcomings and deficiencies are noted. Many contracts are awarded not on the basis of merit but rather on the basis of political affiliation. In all the Western Balkan countries, public procurement systems face multiple deficiencies, and these are in line with those identified by national audit offices, such as the National Audit Office of Kosovo, in their annual auditing reports. These deficiencies include the conclusion of contracts without committed funds; extensive and complex conditions; a lack of open procurement procedures; the adoption of criteria that favour certain operators; the biased evaluation of tenders; the conclusion of contracts with abnormally high prices; a lack of qualified personnel at contracting authorities and economic operators; insufficient time to prepare offers; and major corruption risks in emergency procurement systems.

Management and employment opportunities

Public SOEs are some of the largest employers. But in contrast to the private sector, public SOEs are subject to the vulnerabilities of markets and political and economic fluctuations. The relatively secure employment provided by SOEs is attractive for ordinary people, offering a degree of job security not often seen since the fall of socialist regimes. In exchange, loyalty to the job provider – a political party and its leadership – is an unwritten but well-established contractual clause. This is one of the most powerful and efficient methods of securing unquestionable loyalty and permanence in power; it is also one of the most sustainable ways of buying social peace and assuring political trust. As a result, SOEs are the ‘election prey’ and ‘ATMs’ of ruling parties. Influence and control over public procurement is a part of the corrupt mainstream political culture, as well as of organized corruption. The majority of public enterprise leaders are politically appointed and, more often than not, also politically dismissed. The middle management line is often politically dependent, as well; if not appointed, they are at least required to demonstrate political loyalty in order to keep their jobs. Commonly, the management and decision-making processes of SOEs are influenced by political factors and interests, rather than the pursuit of market, business or marketing strategies. Allegedly, the control and management bodies of SOEs, and specifically their senior members, are commonly appointed by the parties in power via executive power instruments. The construction sector in the Western Balkans is vulnerable to corruption, with public procurement used for political control. Even at lower levels, jobs are often given to people who are loyal to the ruling party. Electoral promises of providing good jobs are often realized via SOEs, and, as big employers, SOEs provide a very solid voter base. This has evidently led to the creation of nests for party employment. Furthermore, these enterprises, which are largely aligned with ruling political parties, provide a competitive advantage for these parties by engaging in corrupt activities and allowing their resources to be used to finance pre-election activities and political campaigns.

This is also a part of corrupt mainstream political culture. Many SOEs are often taking huge losses and are in significant debt – in one country up to 3% of annual GDP, for example. This is well-recognized and reported by state audits and various financial oversight mechanisms, but action is seldom taken against the management. Even when the parties in power change over after an election, they just inherit the state of affairs and, at best, pack posts in upper and middle management with their own political cronies. SOEs are an excellent illustration of the corrupt management and political culture in which

governmental control and oversight bodies are not respected. This applies even to those bodies that are configured to the interests of the political parties in power. Seldom is any judicial action taken against top level management or board members. Therefore, there is a high level of overall impunity: culturally, politically, financially, administratively and judicially.

Some organizational and operational problems that SOEs commonly face across the WB6 are: the signing of unfavourable contracts; problems with liquidity; over-employment, in some cases with overly favourable salaries heavily influenced by politics and nepotism; the duplication of positions; and irregular promotions. Nepotism and political appointments ensure informal access to public resources. Even control and oversight institutions often lack the political independence resources and staff needed to carry out their functions properly. Furthermore, there are no sufficient conflict of interest checks. Often many provisions are not made public, and so proper monitoring is absent or is carried out sporadically. Moreover, decisions and recommendations are at times not implemented. Seldom are judicial actions undertaken to remedy such situations. The absence of proper public procurement planning and strategy is well-noted and was particularly evident during the COVID-19 crisis. The pandemic presented an unprecedented opportunity for corrupt actors and simultaneously highlighted important gaps in the legislation of Western Balkan countries regarding public procurement in states of emergency. States of emergency lead to expedited negotiations and the conclusion of contracts without transparent, fair or competitive public processes. Moreover, the lack of clearly defined criteria in the procurement process results in tangible consequences, as in North Macedonia, where protective equipment and other similar use products were released with considerable discrepancies. Exemptions from regular procedure and the absence of reporting indicate the extent to which the public procurement system is vulnerable to corruption.

There are many examples of improper public procurement management wherein the tender value was known to the bidders so that their bids almost ideally fit the offers. This is particularly noted at the local administration level and in PPP arrangements. Similarly, in some countries, it is not uncommon for the number of bidders to be low and for similar bidders to win public contracts. For example, in Montenegro in 2021, procurement contracts worth approximate €335 million were signed, one fifth of which were concluded based on the submission of a single offer. It appears that there are instances of almost monopolistic positions in terms of tender bidders and winners, indicating the existence of particularly privileged political positions and patronage. On the other hand, favouring certain foreign investors is part of the procurement strategy and planning in some WB6 countries. Therefore, political investment choices in public procurement may be both an instrument of foreign policy and a way of bolstering wealth and power.

All in all, the public procurement sector is highly politicized and often used for political control of the public economy and favouritism of selected private or foreign partners. In the Western Balkan countries, public procurement stands as a good example of organized corruption and political influence and control over public financial instruments and economy. It is an important part of the prevalent pattern of the ruling establishment.

SELECTED EMPIRICAL INDICATORS of ORGANIZED CORRUPTION

The [Global Organized Crime Index](#) is a multi-dimensional tool that assesses the level of criminality and resilience to organized crime for 193 countries along three key pillars – criminal markets, criminal actors, and resilience. Developed over a two-year period, the Index draws from both quantitative and qualitative sources and is underpinned by over 350 expert assessments and evaluations by the GI-TOC’s regional observatories. The objective of the Index is to provide metrics-based information that would allow policymakers and continental and regional bodies to prioritize their interventions on the basis of a holistic assessment of where vulnerabilities lie and equip them with the means to measure the efficacy of their responses to mitigate the impact of organized crime. The Global Organized Crime Index 2023 reveals the continuing rise of organized crime globally, with 83% of the world’s population living in conditions of high criminality. Conversely, the number of people living in conditions of low resilience to organized crime globally has declined significantly: now, 62% of the world’s population, compared to 79.4% in 2021.

State actors remain the most dominant agents in facilitating illicit economies and inhibiting resilience. State-embedded actors remained the most pervasive criminal actor type in 2022. While the degree to which criminality permeates the state apparatus varies across countries and, at all levels, state engagement and/or facilitation of organized crime has grown, with the Index finding human trafficking, arms trafficking and non-renewable resource crimes to have been the most affected. Corruption creates opportunities for illicit activities to thrive, as criminal groups are enabled to operate with reduced risks, while criminal infiltration of state institutions undermines countries’ ability to build resilience and effectively shape policies to counter organized crime.⁵

⁵ Broader consideration about state embedded actors, their role and practical consequences that lead to paradox of „legal state“ see in: Миодраг Лабовиќ, “Системско владеење на правото против системската корупција и организираниот криминал- Стратешка визија со конкретни реално одржливи и практично спроведливи решенија за нашите најголеми проблеми- Како Македонија може да стане функционална држава“, Култура Скопје, 2024, стр. 195-225

CRIMINAL ACTORS

“
State-embedded actors remain the most dominant criminal actor type

Indeed, one of the strongest correlations found among the Index results is between state-embedded actors and overall resilience (-0.79). What this negative correlation suggests is that, as state-embedded actors grow in prominence in a particular area, levels of resilience decline.

STATE-EMBEDDED ACTORS

- ❖ Refers to criminal actors that are embedded in, and act from within the state apparatus.
- ❖ CPI & State-embedded actors are highly correlated (-0.84)
- ❖ In both 2021 and 2023, state-embedded actors dominate the global criminal landscape.

Region	Score	Change
Americas	5.89	+0.28
Europe	4.67	-0.09
Africa	7.12	+0.21
Asia	6.63	+0.17
Oceania	3.43	+0.29

The most authoritative international measurement of corruption is the Transparency International Corruption Perception Index which has quite a long history of 30 years. It started in 1995. It is measuring perception of corruption in some 180 countries all over the world each year last index refers to 2024 and it can be noted that the least vulnerable countries to corruption as perceived by the citizens our countries of Western Europe and European Union while the countries of Eastern Europe score on average 35 out of a hundred points and they are third in terms of the vulnerability to corruption within the eastern and central Europe.

As regards the Balkan peninsula and this can be seen from the table below there are differences between south-eastern European countries that are members of the European Union and those that are not the members of the European Union. For example Greece and Romania have a score of 46 points while Bulgaria has lowest score of 43 points. As regards the Western Balkan countries, the best ranked is Montenegro followed by Kosovo and Albania while Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia are not so well placed. It should be noted for example that while the score of Albania and Kosovo have increased over the past five years in terms of the perception of corruption. It was not the case with Serbia which has moved downwards meaning that citizens have perceived that the situation with corruption in Serbia in the last five years has deteriorated.

Country / Territory	CPI 2024 score	Rank
Albania	42	80
Bosnia and Herzegovina	33	114
Bulgaria	43	76
Greece	49	59
Kosovo	44	73
Montenegro	46	65
North Macedonia	40	88
Romania	46	65
Serbia	35	105

The criminal markets index for the south-eastern European countries shows that Serbia, Bulgaria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Romania, and Montenegro are above the average criminal market scores on the global level while North Macedonia, Albania, Kosovo, and Greece a little bit lower. On the other hand, the criminal actor scores for Serbia, Montenegro, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Greece, Bulgaria and Albania are above the global average while the score for North Macedonia is a bit lower.

However, looking at the criminal actor types, it is very clear that the state embedded actors are predominant in Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Greece but as well as North Macedonia, in Albania, Kosovo, and a bit less in Romania. It can be also noted that criminal networks and private sector as criminal actors are very much present in all the Western Balkan countries as well as in Greece and Bulgaria.

CONCLUDING OBSERVATIONS

No law is implemented on its own, and there is no law that cannot be bypassed. A culture of integrity and lawfulness is vital for good governance. The Western Balkan countries are still in search of such a political culture of integrity. Overall, the WB6 countries have made real progress towards regulating and controlling the financing of political parties and elections, SOEs and public procurement. The role of the international community, including the donor community, in providing guidelines and standards and periodic reviews has increased the compatibility of legislation with European and international standards. However, changes to the laws have not been sufficiently internalized in the political culture to make parties transparent, accountable and responsible servants for society or the state. This is the urgent task for all the actors – political parties, governments, parliaments and civil society members – in the promotion of a political culture of integrity.

Yet there is no ample mandate for the control institutions in the Western Balkans to enable a comprehensive approach. Instead, as is the case in other areas, they are very narrow, fragmented and bureaucratically squeezed. Coordination and cooperation with other control structures is clearly absent. Oversight is not only a matter for the control institutions, but also for civil society: NGOs, academics, investigative journalists and the media. Such a role for civil society in the Western Balkans is well recognized, and there are many examples of civil society publicly reporting, denouncing and protesting against political abuses and illicit financing. Yet there is no appreciation for such a role. Even in

some electoral control processes, there is no parity between the representatives of the political parties concerned and the civil observers. Moreover, the role of parliaments in exercising an oversight function is very marginal in the Western Balkans. This is a huge obstacle to promoting institutional accountability. A political culture of integrity requires the institutionalization of civil society's oversight role.

As noted earlier the notion of organized corruption points out to a nexus between organized crime and corruption. Indeed, corruption enables and is enabled by organized crime and corruption is both a driver of organized crime and a barrier to resilience. This nexus is partially recognised both by the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC), which treats corruption as one of its criminal offences, and by the United Nations Convention against Corruption (UNCAC), which states that corruption allows organized crime, terrorism, and other threats to human security to flourish.

Organized corruption refers to the involvement in or use of various forms of corruption and related activities by an interest organization, criminal or not, which profits from its position of power and/or political coverage to gain financial, political or social benefits. Organized corruption can be manifested on a high level with the involvement of the top management of the government and political parties and the control of the public state-owned enterprises party and elections financing and marketing. It can be involved in the mezzo-sphere which is typical for the relationship between political structures and the private economic sector as, for example, in the procurement. Finally, nexus is clearly present in the underground through the typical involvement of organized crime through the legalization of illicit profits – there, corruption is one of the main vehicles for such organized endeavour.

Changing such a state of affairs requires deep reforms. Yet these reforms are not possible as long as the SOEs and much of the public procurement processes are under complete control of the political parties in power and considered to be electoral prey. Furthermore, the manner in which political parties seek to obtain funds and maintain power through control of economic and employment opportunities is a matter for society as a whole. It is a call to arms for the democratic values of transparency and, above all, honesty and devotion to the state. Therefore, in all WB6 countries, a change in the political culture is needed, and organized corruption must be dismantled as a prevalent pattern of the ruling establishment.

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